

Characteristics of Emergency Calls (Rhesus Call) in the case of neuroemergence at the Emergency Department at Sanglah General Hospital Period January 2016 to January 2018

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ABSTRACT Objective: To determine the characteristics of neurology cases in the ER Sanglah Hospital who underwent an emergency call period from January 2016 to 2018. **Material and Methods:** This research is a descriptive cross-sectional study using secondary data. This study is total sampling method. The study used a questionnaire, data obtained from all cases of neurology who underwent an emergency call within the study period recorded in the emergency call register. Descriptive analysis using SPSS 21.00 for windows. **Results:** Samples obtained in 76 cases. The majority of cases in this study were men (n=40, 52.6%) and the mean age of all cases was 55.05 (\pm 15.23). The major cases are reported hemorrhagic stroke (n=40, 52.6%), intracranial infection (n=10, 13.2%), ischemic stroke (n=9, 11.8%), epilepsy (n=3, 3.9%), and malignancy (n=3, 3.9%). Most cases had a secondary diagnosis that accompanied the primary diagnosis (n=54, 71.1%). The mean duration of treatment in the emergency room before an emergency call (pre rhesus call) was 308 (\pm 629.99) minutes. The mean duration of treatment in the emergency department after an emergency call (post rhesus call) was 540 (\pm 766.1) minutes. The dominant case outcome was death (n = 68, 89.5%). **Conclusion:** The most common cases undergoing emergency calls are a hemorrhagic stroke, intracranial infection, ischemic stroke, epilepsy, and malignancy. The majority of clinical outcomes in each case were deaths. Analytical research needs to be done to find out which variables can influence clinical outcomes.

KEYWORDS rhesus call, emergency, intracranial, outcomes

Introduction

Hospital emergency codes are a form of emergency treatment and used throughout the world. Emergency codes are a form of signal to the medical team that there is an emergency and

require immediate treatment. Emergency codes are intended to be able to start appropriate, effective and efficient treatment, to improve the patient's prognosis [1].

Neurological disorders is a health disorder with a high number of visits to the emergency department (ED). One study showed that the proportion of neurological cases in all patients who came to the emergency room was 8% to 15% [2]. Emergencies in the field of neurology are associated with high morbidity and mortality, as well as significant economic burdens [3]. The most common neurological emergencies are cerebrovascular disease, headaches and epilepsy [4].

Sanglah Central General Hospital (RSUP) is a referral centre hospital in Bali. Sanglah Hospital has an emergency manage-

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ment system called the emergency call (Rhesus Call). Emergency calls are intended for cases with airway problems that are not roomy, inadequate breathing, hemodynamically unstable, and decreased awareness [5]. The proportion of all neurology cases undergoing emergency calls has not recorded. The purpose of this study was to determine the characteristics of neurology cases in the Sanglah General Hospital emergency room who underwent emergency calls for the period from January 2016 to 2018.

Material and Method

This study uses a descriptive cross-sectional design by collecting data using secondary data from the emergency call register at Sanglah Hospital in the period of January 2016 to January 2018. The study conducted in May-June 2018 at the Sanglah Hospital in Denpasar, Bali. This study's affordable population is a neurology case that underwent an emergency call during the study period. All cases that met the eligibility criteria included as research subjects. The patient over 18 years old, with acute neurological symptoms, registered as neurological triage patients and rhesus calls. Medical records of neurological cases, not emergency cases and not entirely recorded in the register excluded from the study. The variables assessed in this study include demographic data, primary diagnosis of cases, secondary diagnoses, namely other diagnoses that accompany the primary diagnosis. The principal diagnoses are the diagnosis listed in the emergency call register and confirmed by the results of clinical examination and supporting examination. The primary diagnosis divided into five groups. They are a stroke, epilepsy, intracranial infections, malignancy, and others are acute neurological abnormalities that cannot classify in the five categories above. The duration of treatment variable divided into two groups, namely the length of treatment in the emergency room before the emergency call (pre rhesus call) and the period of medicine in the emergency room after the emergency call (post rhesus call). Outcomes categorised into two groups died in the emergency room within the first 72 hours and inpatients representing cases transferred to the inpatient ward — data analysis descriptive using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 21 for windows.

Result

The number of secondary data obtained during the study period was 76 cases — a general description of the subject presented in Table 1. The majority of cases recorded in this study were men ($n = 40$, 52.6%). The age of the recorded cases ranged from 20 years to 98 years, with an average age of 55.05 (± 15.23). The majority of cases obtained were hemorrhagic strokes ($n = 40$, 52.6%). Most cases had a secondary diagnosis that accompanied the primary diagnosis ($n = 54$, 71.1%). Secondary diagnoses recorded include hypertension, diabetes mellitus, cardiological abnormalities, sepsis, and other categories.

The mean duration of treatment in the emergency room before an emergency call (pre rhesus call) was 308 (± 629.99) minutes. The mean duration of treatment in the emergency department after an emergency call (post rhesus call) was 540 (± 766.1) minutes. The dominant case outcome was death ($n = 68$, 89.5%).

The clinical outcome of each case is grouped into death and hospitalization. The primary characteristics of each case concerning clinical outcomes are shown in table 2.

Age variables grouped into two based on the age limit of geriatrics, which is more than or equal to 60 years and less than

60 years. All types of cases mostly experience clinical outcomes in the form of death. Only cases of epilepsy and hemorrhagic stroke have inpatient outcomes. Emergency calls made less than 20 minutes or more than 20 minutes after the patient's visit to the emergency room most of the clinical outcomes died.

Discussion

The most common using emergency call is hemorrhagic stroke (52.6%). A study in Brazil found that the prevalence of the most frequent appearance was a case of cerebrovascular disorders [1]. Research by Ojaghihaghghi in 2017 concluded that the incidence of ischemic stroke (359 cases) was higher than stroke hemorrhagic (144 cases). Clinical symptoms assessed as parameters in the study included awareness as measured by the Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS), the hemorrhagic stroke had a lower GCS mean of 8.97 than an ischemic stroke of 12.67 [6]. This study found mydriasis 86.8% of hemorrhagic stroke. Clinical symptoms showed the condition of hemorrhagic stroke was worse than ischemic stroke. It might correlate with a high prevalence of emergency call for hemorrhagic stroke. Further analysis is needed to find out the correlation magnitude [6,7].

Eighty per cent of hemorrhagic stroke cases die within the first 72 hours. Despite emergency calls and only seventeen per cent of cases have successfully transferred to the inpatient ward — clinical outcomes after being in the inpatient room not recorded in this study. Case fatality rates in hemorrhagic strokes have extensively studied and reached high proportions. Intracranial and subarachnoid haemorrhage occurred at 42.0% and 28.7%. They concluded that one-third of hemorrhagic stroke cases would die within the first month, and the risk of death will continue to increase until the first year [8]. Fold in the hyperacute phase, after one week, and the risk becomes 2.5 times. While the mortality rate in ischemic stroke was presented to be 25.9% with a case fatality rate in the first week was 1.8% within 735 minutes (12.2 hours) [9].

Brain infection included abscess, bacterial meningitis, toxoplasmosis, and tetanus. The results of this study indicate that intracranial infection cases are the second most common neurological cases using emergency call facilities. Emergency calls made to patients with brain infections due to various causes such as seizures, haemodynamic disorders due to sepsis, and airway disorders due to breath muscle spasms. Each case of the intracranial disease has a predisposing factor related to its clinical outcome [10]. All instances of intracranial infection in this study died. It is correlating with the theory that meningitis has high fatality rates between 2% to 30%.[10] Meningitis mortality rates are also high, reaching 32% and 10% to 20% of cases will get sequelae [11]. The aetiology of death in brain infection is meningitis. Encephalitis is complications during the acute phase due to secondary brain damage — a study conducted at the hospital dr. Cipto Mangunkusumo Jakarta to assess the mortality of meningitis by taking cases of meningitis from January 1997 to December 2005, and the result of meningitis mortality was 41.8% [11]. The mean length of treatment for intracranial infection after an emergency call until death was 804 minutes (13.4 hours).

Cases of malignancy and epilepsy were each found in 3 facts in this study. All matters of malignancy in this study were primary intracerebral fatalities, and all instances died from cerebral herniation. The mean duration of treatment for malignant cases after rhesus call was 321 minutes (5.5 hours). Two examples of epilepsy in this study died, and one fact treated in intensive care. The epilepsy case is a case that has erected with a history of

Table 1 Subject Characteristic

Characteristic	n(%)
Age (Mean \pm SD)	
≥ 60 years old	
< 60 years old	
Sex	
Male	
Female	55.05 (\pm 15.23)
	29 (38.2)
	47 (61.8)
	40 (52.6)
	36 (47.4)
Primary Diagnostic	
Stroke Hemorrhagic	40 (52.6)
Stroke Non-Hemorrhagic	9 (11.8)
Epilepsy	3 (3.9)
Intracranial infection	10 (13.2)
Neoplasma	3 (3.9)
Others	11 (14.5)
Secondary Diagnostic	
Hypertension	24 (31.6)
Diabetes Mellitus	22 (28.9)
Anomaly Cardiology	13 (17.1)
Septic	9 (11.8)
Others	6 (7.9)
No diagnostic	2 (2.6)
Duration pre rhesus call (Means \pm SD)	308.28 \pm 629.9 minutes
Duration post rhesus call (Means \pm SD)	540.48 \pm 766.1 minutes
Outcome	68 (89.5)
Death	8 (10.5)
In Patient	

Table 2 Characteristics of Outcome

Characteristics	Outcome n (%)	
	Death	In-patient
Age (Means \pm SD)		
≥ 60 years	25 (86.2)	4 (13.8)
< 60 years	43 (91.5)	4 (8.5)
Sex	32 (88.9)	4 (1.1)
Male	36 (90)	4 (10)
Female		
Primary Diagnostic		
Stroke Hemorrhagic	33 (82.5)	7 (17.5)
Stroke Non-Hemorrhagic	9 (100)	0
Epilepsy	2 (66.7)	1(33.3)
Intracranial process	10 (100)	0
Neoplasma	3 (100)	0
Others	11 (100)	0
Secondary Diagnostic		
Yes	52 (91.3)	5 (8.7)
No	19 (86.4)	3 (13.6)
Duration pre rhesus call		
≤ 20 minutes	33 (86.6)	5 (13.2)
> 20 minutes	35 (92.1)	4 (7.9)
Duration post rhesus call		
≤ 300 minutes	37 (88.1)	5 (11.9)
> 300 minute	31 (89.5)	3 (3.6)

previous treatment. These results are consistent with previous studies that chronic epilepsy accounts for up to 40% of deaths in all epilepsy cases[12]. The average length of treatment for epilepsy cases is 156 minutes (2.6 hours). The average duration of therapy after rhesus call until death is the shortest compared to other situations is a case of epilepsy.

The duration of the emergency call in cases since coming to the emergency room both in the group was less than 20 minutes or more than 20 minutes; the clinical outcome that remained dominant was death. Seventy-three per cent of those who die has a co-diagnosis other than the primary diagnosis. The patient's clinical age, diagnosis, and other accompanying diagnoses need to be further analyzed to determine their effect on the clinical outcome of each case.

Conclusion

The most common neurological cases in emergency rooms with rhesus call are a hemorrhagic stroke, brain infection, ischemic stroke, epilepsy, and malignancy. The majority of clinical outcomes in each case were deaths. Analytical research needs to be done to find out which variables can influence clinical outcomes.

Competing interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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